

Epoxidation of cyclohexene catalysed by Mn^{II} supported on α -titanium arsenate as catalyst and dry TBHP as an oxidant

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Abstract : Manganese supported on α -titanium arsenate $\{\alpha\text{-TiMn}^{II}\text{As}\}$ was synthesized by ion-exchange method and characterized by DSC. Its catalytic activity is reported for epoxidation of cyclohexene using dry *tert*-butylhydroperoxide (TBHP) as an oxidant. In the epoxidation reaction, cyclohexene was oxidized to cyclohexene oxide, cyclohexenol and cyclohexenone. The effect of catalyst concentration and cyclohexene concentration was studied on epoxidation of cyclohexene and optimum concentrations were obtained for maximum selectivity for epoxidation of cyclohexene. A maximum selectivity (86.09%) for epoxidation of cyclohexene was observed for $\alpha\text{-TiMn}^{II}\text{As}$ /dry TBHP system after 4 h of reaction when concentrations of catalyst and substrate were 0.20 mmol and 20 mmol respectively. The mechanism for epoxidation of cyclohexene catalyzed by $\alpha\text{-TiMn}^{II}\text{As}$ /dry TBHP system is proposed.

Keywords : Epoxidation, cyclohexane, TBHP, manganese(II), titanium arsenate.

The ion-exchange method of catalyst immobilization on layered compounds is simpler compared to the procedures required for attachment of complexes to polymers¹. Ion-exchange method of catalyst immobilization on layered compounds is better because it provides temperature- and solvent-stable inorganic layered exchangers of known structure as support¹. The compound α -titanium arsenate has a structure with zeolite type cages and it behaves as a cation exchange². Therefore it is interesting to investigate the immobilization of catalytically active Mn^{II} ions on α -titanium arsenate and potential of Mn^{II} ion-substituted supports as catalysts. In present paper, we are reporting our results on the synthesis and catalytic behaviour of Mn^{II} supported on an inorganic cation exchanger α -titanium arsenate, $\alpha\text{-TiMn}^{II}\text{As}$, for the epoxidation of cyclohexene using dry *tert*-butylhydroperoxide (TBHP) as an oxidant.

Results and discussion

Characterization of catalysts : The catalysts, $\alpha\text{-TiMn}^{II}\text{As}$ was prepared by exchanging surface protons (hydrogen ions) from $\alpha\text{-TiH}_2\text{As}$ with Mn^{II} ions. The total number of released hydrogen ions $[H^+]$ in the exchange reaction determined the total uptake of Mn^{II} ions on the surface of $\alpha\text{-TiH}_2\text{As}$. The number of hydrogen

ions $[H^+]$ released in the exchange reaction in each trial was calculated from pH value of the metal solution at equilibrium³. The process of attaining equilibrium was repeated until the subsequent pH change was negligible and the total uptake of Mn^{II} ions is determined from the total change in the pH value in all trials.

The initial pH of 0.1 M solution of $(CH_3COO)_2Mn$ was 7.14, however when this solution was used for up-loading of Mn^{II} on $\alpha\text{-TiH}_2\text{As}$, the total uptake of Mn^{II} ions was not significant equal to 0.00097 meq/g in five trials. To increase the uptake of Mn^{II} ions on $\alpha\text{-TiH}_2\text{As}$, the pH of the 0.1 M solution of $(CH_3COO)_2Mn$ was adjusted up to 4.11 by adding CH_3COOH (pH = 4.11) because an increase in uptake of Mn^{II} on $\alpha\text{-TiH}_2\text{As}$ is reported when the pH of the solution was below 4.0⁴. By using this solutions, the final pH value of $(CH_3COO)_2Mn.4H_2O$ solution in the 1st trial, was 3.75; thus $[H^+] = 1.778 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M/L} = 8.891 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol per 50 ml}$. Converting this to meq/g, when the weight of the sample ($\alpha\text{-TiH}_2\text{As}$) was 1.0 g, thus $8.891 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol per 50 ml}$ is equal to 0.008 meq/g. Three such trials were required after which change in pH was negligible. The total uptake of Mn^{II} ions on $\alpha\text{-TiH}_2\text{As}$, obtained by summing uptakes of Mn^{II} ions in all trials, was 0.013 meq/g (8, 5, 0 meq/g at pH 3.75–3.99).

DSC studies of α -TiH₂As showed two endotherms at 175 °C and 550 °C. Endotherm at 175 °C was due to loss of external water molecules while endotherm at 550 °C was due to loss of one more water molecule due to condensation. In case of α -TiMn^{II}As, only one endotherm at 175 °C was observed. The absence of the endotherm at 550 °C indicated absence of any replaceable H⁺ ion. These results confirm that hydrogen form of titanium arsenate is converted into manganous substituted titanium arsenate.

Catalytic epoxidation : The epoxidation of various cyclic olefins and norbornene using α -TiMn^{II}As/dry TBHP system were studied under nitrogen atmosphere. The results are compiled in Table 1. It was observed that all cyclic olefins undergo epoxidation and corresponding epoxide was obtained. In all cases, the yield of epoxide was more in epoxidation under nitrogen atmosphere compared to that under atmospheric air. Similar observation is reported in the epoxidation reaction with CrO₃/TBHP system⁵. The epoxidation reaction is inhibited by water while accelerated by nondonor polar solvents⁶ and azeotropically dried solution of TBHP in benzene is very stable to storage⁷. Thus instead of commercial TBHP (70% in water), dry TBHP in benzene was used as the oxidant in the epoxidation reactions. The yields of the products were based on the internal standard (dodecane) and the consumption of TBHP was determined iodometrically. It was observed that cyclopentene, *cis*-cyclooctene and norbornene gave corresponding epoxides selectively. Oxidation of cyclohexene gave cyclohexene oxide, cyclohexenol and cyclohexenone. The epoxidation of cyclohexene as substrate was carried out using

α -TiMn^{II}As/dry TBHP system and effect of presence of water, concentrations of catalyst and substrate on selectivity of epoxide is studied.

In similar experimental conditions, α -TiH₂As and α -TiMn^{II}As were separately tested for epoxidation of cyclohexene with dry TBHP as the oxidant and it was found that while α -TiH₂As was catalytically inactive, α -TiMn^{II}As was active for the epoxidation reaction. Therefore the exchange of Mn^{II} ion with hydrogen converted a non-catalyst, α -TiH₂As, into active catalysts for epoxidation of cyclohexene. The catalytic epoxidation of cyclohexene, catalyzed by α -TiMn^{II}As/dry TBHP system can be explained by the reaction :

The formation of cyclohexenol and cyclohexenone in the epoxidation reaction suggest that a free radical pathway is operative.

The kinetics of cyclohexene epoxidation using α -TiMn^{II}As/dry TBHP system was monitored at different time-intervals. It was observed that initial 1 h was the induction period of the catalyst for epoxidation reaction during which no product formation took place and the reaction was complete in 4 h after which no further epoxide formation took place. The percentage conversion of cyclohexene kept on increasing continuously with time. The percentage formation of cyclohexenol and cyclohexenone were a maximum in first 1.5 h and then it decreased with time. The percentage selectivity of epoxide reached a maximum (86.09%) after 4 h and then

Table 1. Epoxidation of olefins catalyzed by α -TiMn^{II}As/dry TBHP system

Sl. no.	Olefins	Products	Conversion of selectivity (%)	
			Olefins	Epoxide
1.		8.51	100	
2.		18.65	86.09 12.70 1.21	
3.		32.11	100	
4.		19.10	96.99 3.01	

started decreasing. The demetallation produced free metal ions, which increased homolytic decomposition of TBHP, which in turn increased the selectivity of cyclohexenol and cyclohexenone. Due to increase in selectivity of cyclohexenol and cyclohexenone, the selectivity of cyclohexene oxide decreased.

Effect of catalyst concentration : The effect of the concentration of catalyst, α -TiMn^{II}As, in the epoxidation of cyclohexene using dry TBHP as an oxidant was studied and the results are given in Table 2. It was observed that the conversion of cyclohexene, the yield of cyclohexene oxide and the yield of other products increase with increase in the catalyst concentration, however the rates of formation of cyclohexene oxide and other products are different at different concentrations of the catalyst. The selectivity of epoxide increased with increase of concentration of the catalyst in the beginning (upto 0.20 mmol), reached a maximum and then started decreasing. At 0.20 mmol concentration of the catalyst, the selectivity of cyclohexene oxide was a maximum (86.09%), while selectivity of other products was a minimum (cyclohexenol = 12.71% and cyclohexenone = 1.20%). Above 0.20 mmol concentration of the catalyst, the increase in yields of cyclohexenol and cyclohexenone are more compared to increase of yield of cyclohexene oxide. Consequently, the selectivity of the epoxide de-

creased at the higher concentration of the catalyst. Similar observation are reported in case of Mn(TPP)Cl/NaOCl system⁸ and Fe(SALEN)Cl/PhIO system⁹. It was also observed that with change of concentration of the catalyst, the change in the selectivity of cyclohexenone was relatively lesser than that of other products.

The effect of the concentration of substrate (cyclohexene) in the epoxidation reaction using α -TiMn^{II}As/dry TBHP system was studied. The results of the conversion of cyclohexene, selectivity of products for different concentrations of cyclohexene are summarized in Table 3. The concentration of cyclohexene was varied from 1 to 25 mmol and it was observed that the yield of all the products increased with increase in concentration of cyclohexene. The selectivity of cyclohexene oxide reached a maximum (86.09%) for 20 mmol concentration of cyclohexene. In the epoxidation of cyclohexene catalyzed by α -TiMn^{II}As/TBHP (70% in water), the conversion of cyclohexene was 18.84% and the selectivity of the epoxide was 79.24%, when the concentrations of catalyst and substrate were 0.20 mmol and 20 mmol respectively. In similar experimental conditions by use of dry TBHP in benzene as the oxidant, the conversion of cyclohexene was almost the same (18.65%) while the selectivity of the epoxide was more (86.09%).

Competitive epoxidation : The relative rate of the

Table 2. Effect of concentration of catalyst on the epoxidation of cyclohexene catalyzed by α -TiMn^{II}As/dry TBHP system

Sl. no.	Concentration of catalyst (mmol)	Conversion of cyclohexene (%)	Selectivity of cyclohexene oxide (%)	Selectivity of cyclohexenol (%)	Selectivity of cyclohexenone (%)
1.	0.10	14.81	85.95	12.83	1.22
2.	0.20	17.55	86.09	12.07	1.21
3.	0.30	19.09	84.15	14.49	1.36
4.	0.40	19.43	83.01	15.50	1.49
5.	0.50	19.73	81.75	16.68	1.57

Table 3. Effect of concentration of catalyst on the epoxidation of cyclohexene catalyzed by α -TiMn^{II}As/dry TBHP system

Sl. no.	Concentration of catalyst (mmol)	Conversion of cyclohexene (%)	Selectivity of cyclohexene oxide (%)	Selectivity of cyclohexenol (%)	Selectivity of cyclohexenone (%)
1.	1	1.93	80.83	15.58	3.36
2.	5	3.66	83.90	13.37	2.73
3.	10	5.03	84.29	13.02	2.68
4.	15	16.70	85.87	12.87	1.26
5.	20	17.55	86.09	12.70	1.21
6.	25	19.97	85.58	13.17	1.45

epoxidation of cyclic olefins are cyclopentene (0.53) cyclohexene (1.0), *cis*-cyclooctene (1.19) and norbornene (2.0) with α -TiMn^{II}As/dry TBHP system. The order of reactivity of cyclic olefins decreased in the order, norbornene > *cis*-cyclooctene > cyclohexene > cyclopentene. The higher rates of epoxidation with norbornene and *cis*-cyclooctene compared to cyclohexene indicate that the olefin is not rigidly coordinated to the metal center during epoxidation. Had olefin been coordinated to metal center, than the rate of epoxidation of olefin having a carbon atom number higher than cyclohexene would have been lower, contrary to observation with α -TiMn^{II}As/dry TBHP system. Hydrogenation of olefins using RhCl(PPh₃)₃ showed that the rate of hydrogenation decreased with increasing olefin ring size C₅ > C₆ > C₇ > C₈ > C₉ as coordination of olefin to the metal center takes place in the transition state¹⁰. Higher rates of epoxidation for norbornene and cyclooctene have been observed for Fe(SALEN)Cl/PhIO⁹ and Mn(SALEN)NCS/PhIO catalytic systems. It suggests that the conformation, the bond angle strain and the torsional strain play important roles in governing the relative rates of the epoxidations of the cyclic olefins.

Mechanism :

Scheme 1 explains the mechanism of epoxidation of cyclohexene catalyzed by α -TiMn^{II}As/dry TBHP system. Initial complex formation between metal catalyst, α -TiMn^{II}As, and *tert*-butyl hydroperoxide renders the peroxidic oxygen more electrophilic and hence more labile to attack by an olefinic double bond. The remaining *tert*-butoxy (O^tBu) radical is a worse leaving group as far as the catalytic reaction is concerned. Cyclohexene reacted with *tert*-butoxy radical to form cyclohexenol, which further oxidized to cyclohexenone. Thus epoxidation by α -TiMn^{II}As/dry TBHP system involved two competing reactions, viz. (a) epoxidation and (b) homolytic decomposition of TBHP. The results on catalytic epoxidation demonstrated that the performance of manganese supported on α -titanium arsenate { α -TiMn^{II}As} depended on the relative rates of metal catalyzed epoxidation and metal catalyzed decomposition of TBHP. In case of metal catalyzed epoxidation, the high selectivity of epoxidation is obtained due to the electrophilic attack on the olefin that involves heterolytic mechanism¹¹. The Mn^{II} ion, which was present on the surface of the heterogeneous catalyst, α -TiMn^{II}As, provided selectivity for the epoxidation and also suppressed the side products, which were formed due to homolytic decomposition of TBHP. The observation of the highest relative rate of epoxidation by

norbornene in competitive epoxidation of cyclic olefins confirms that complex formation takes place between metal catalyst and TBHP. If olefin had coordinated to the metal

Scheme 1

catalyst in the epoxidation reaction then a reverse order of relative rate of epoxidation would have been observed¹⁰.

In the proposed mechanism, the introduced Mn^{II} ions act as the active sites for oxygen transfer and the reactivity of oxygen transfer depends on the strength of metal-oxygen (Mn-O) bond. Thus the catalytic inactiveness of the hydrogen form of titanium arsenate, α -TiH₂As, can be explained by the absence of active sites for oxygen transfer¹². Analogous mechanisms are suggested for epoxidation of cyclohexene catalyzed by molybdenum¹¹, boron¹³ and titanium supported on silica¹⁴.

The catalyst, α -TiMn^{II}As, was synthesized and studied with dry TBHP as the oxidant for epoxidation of cyclohexene. A maximum selectivity for epoxidation of cyclohexene (86.09%) was observed after 4 h of reaction when concentrations of catalyst and substrate were 0.20 mmol and 20 mmol respectively. A mechanism is proposed, which satisfactorily explains the catalytic activity of the α -TiMn^{II}As/dry TBHP system for the epoxidation of cyclohexene.

Experimental

Starting materials :

Sodium arsenate (E. Merck), 15% w/v titanate chloride solution (B.D.H.) and manganous acetate (E. Merck) were of reagent grade. All starting alkenes viz. cyclopentene, cyclohexene, *cis*-cyclooctene and norbornene (E. Merck) were checked by gas chromato-

graphy (G.C.) to ensure that no oxidation products were present before reaction. The solution of dry TBHP in benzene was obtained by careful azeotropic distillation of the aqueous 70% commercial solution (E. Merck) according to the procedure described by Sharpless *et al.*¹⁵. The strength of dry TBHP was estimated by a known procedure¹⁵. The reference sample of epoxide was prepared by the standard procedure¹⁶. Analytical gas chromatography was carried out on a gas chromatograph with dual flame ionization detector and an attached XY recorder. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) studies of hydrogen form of α -titanium arsenate, α -TiH₂As, and Mn^{II} supported on α -titanium arsenate, α -TiMn^{II}As, were done on a differential scanning calorimeter at a heating rate of 10 °C/min.

The catalyst was prepared in two steps. In the first step, α -TiH₂As, { α -Ti(HAsO₄)₂.H₂O}, was synthesized by a known procedure². In the second step, hydrogen of α -TiH₂As was substituted by a Mn^{II} ions to synthesize α -TiMn^{II}As. For preparation of α -TiMn^{II}As, stock solution of manganous acetate (0.1 N) was prepared and initial pH of the solution was measured on a digital pH meter. Then 100 ml of this solution was vigorously stirred with 1.0 g of α -TiH₂As by a magnetic-stirrer for one hour. The pH of the solution was measured at every ten minutes. The uptake of Mn^{II} ion is determined from the change in pH. After attainment of equilibrium, the solution was filtered. The filtered solid was added to a fresh solution (100 ml) of manganous acetate and the process was repeated again. The process was repeated until there was no further change in pH of the solution. The total uptake of Mn^{II} ions is the sum of uptakes of Mn^{II} ions in each trial. The cation exchanger, so obtained, was filtered and washed with distilled water and dried at 40°.

Epoxidation of olefins : Epoxidation of all olefins were carried out in a three-necked round bottom flask (100 ml) under nitrogen atmosphere. Nitrogen was flushed for 10 min through the flask, which was loaded with benzene (10 ml), olefins (20 mmol), catalyst { α -TiMn^{II}As} (0.2 mmol) and dodecane (an internal standard, 0.1 ml). After nitrogen flushing, TBHP (4 mmol) was added and the contents of the flask were heated at 80 °C on a magnetic hot plate for 4 h with continuous stirring. After completion of the reaction, the contents of the flask were cooled in an ice-bath and the catalyst was filtered out. In the filtrate, 10 ml of freshly prepared 10% solution of sodium sulfite was added drop by drop under constant stirring to destroy unreacted TBHP. The products were extracted with ether and then dried using anhydrous magne-

sium sulphate. These products were analyzed by gas chromatography using XE-60 as column at 120 °C.

The effect of catalyst concentration on the epoxidation of cyclohexene was studied by changing the concentration of the catalyst, α -TiMn^{II}As, from 0.1 to 0.5 mmol. The reactions were carried out by taking catalyst { α -TiMn^{II}As}, cyclohexene (20 mmol), TBHP (4 mmol) and dodecane (0.1 ml) in benzene (10 ml) under nitrogen atmosphere. The contents of the flask were heated at 80 °C for 4 h with continuous stirring. After completion of the reactions, the products were extracted and analyzed in the same way as done in the case of epoxidation of cyclohexene. The effect of cyclohexene concentration was studied by taking catalyst { α -TiMn^{II}As} (0.2 mmol), TBHP (4 mmol), dodecane (0.1 ml) and six different concentrations of cyclohexene (1, 5, 10, 15, 20 and 25 mmol) in benzene (10 ml) under nitrogen atmosphere. The contents of the flask were heated at 80 °C for 4 h with continuous stirring. After completion of the reactions, the products were extracted and analyzed in the same way as done in the case of epoxidation of cyclohexene.

The competitive epoxidation of cyclic olefins, viz. cyclopentene, cyclohexene, *cis*-cyclooctene, and norbornene were studied by mixing cyclohexene (20 mmol), another cyclic olefin (20 mmol), catalyst { α -TiMn^{II}As} (0.4 mmol), TBHP (8 mmol), and dodecane (0.1 ml) in benzene (10 ml) in a three-necked round bottom flask (100 ml) under nitrogen atmosphere. The contents of the flask were heated at 80 °C for 4 h with continuous stirring. After completion of the reaction, the products were extracted in the same way as extracted in the case of epoxidation of cyclohexene. Two columns XE-60 (at 120 °C) and Carbowax-20M (at 90 °C) of the gas chromatograph were used to analyze the products.

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